

REACTIVE SYNTHESIS: A PROMISING ROUTE FOR THE IN-SITU FORMATION OF NANOSIZED REINFORCEMENTS IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The present paper describes a new synthesis route for particulate reinforcement metal matrix composites. The process consists in the chemical reaction at high temperature between precursor materials to form in-situ both the matrix and the particles of the reinforcing phase. The main criteria that have to be considered to determine if a given matrix/reinforcement couple can be obtained by this route are illustrated on specific examples. The main advantages are the quality of the matrix/reinforcement interface that is formed in-situ by a nucleation/growth mechanism (free of oxide layers) the homogeneity of the microstructure without any clustering effect, even for high volume fraction of reinforcement. Moreover, nano-sized particles of reinforcement with a mean that is about 30 nm can be obtained without any handling of nano-sized powders. The interest of this route is also illustrated by mechanical properties characterized by high strength values associated with a failure elongation of 6%.

1 INTRODUCTION

Among the different class of metal matrix composites (MMC), particulate reinforcement composites (PRMMC) are certainly the most widely used, and especially the Aluminium or Magnesium based matrices, because of their low density that is interesting for lightweight components. Several drawbacks limit the utilization of PRMMC to replace lightweight alloys. Among these drawbacks, one can cite the brittleness of the particles and the heterogeneity in the reinforcement distribution that induce an embrittlement of the composite as compared to its matrix, or the machining costs associated to the hardness of the reinforcement particles. During the last decades, the use of nanosized particles has been envisaged as a solution to limit the probability of intrinsic flaws, to fulfill high composite yield strength and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and also to facilitate machining of composite pieces.

First, most of the synthesis routes (flux and squeeze casting, powder metallurgy, ...) that have been studied are facing some safety difficulties because of the manipulation of nanosized particles. Indeed, the cost of processes dealing with nanosized particles that ensure safety of workers and limit the

release of nanoparticles in the environment is increased. As a consequence these new nanoparticulate reinforcement MMC are not competitive with classical lightweight alloys from a cost standpoint.

Second, these synthesis routes are also facing technical difficulties as the heterogeneity in the reinforcement distribution in the matrix and the presence of oxide layer covering the added reinforcements that leads to degradation of interfacial bonding. These two main phenomena lead to a decrease in the mechanical properties of the final PRMMC material.

The in-situ synthesis of both the matrix and the reinforcement particles is a promising route to produce PRMMC materials. One can expect from the in-situ synthesis the formation of well-crystallized particles, with a limited number of flaws and also good interfacial bonding between matrix and particles with the total absence of oxide layers. In this route, also call “reactive synthesis”, starting materials are micro-sized precursors which, following a chemical reaction occurring at high temperature, will form both the metallic matrix and the ceramic reinforcements. Moreover, this process is of particular interest in the synthesis of MMC with nanosized reinforcement as no manipulation of precursor at the nanoscale is required.

2 PRINCIPLE OF IN-SITU FORMATION OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

Several processing routes for manufacturing of MMC materials by in-situ technics exist [1]. The specificity of the synthesis route proposed in the present paper can be illustrated in the specific case of an aluminium (Al) base matrix composite reinforced by titanium carbide (TiC) particles. As illustrated in Figure 1, the two phases are not in thermodynamic equilibrium at low temperature but equilibrium is established at higher temperature. According to Viala et al. [2] the transition occurs with the invariant reaction (1) at about 812°C:

Figure 1: isothermal sections of the Al-C-Ti ternary system in two different ranges of temperature (according to [2])

As a consequence of these phase equilibria, a specific mixture of Al_3Ti and carbon (C), given by the intersection of the line from C to Al_3Ti and and the tie-line at about 1000°C between Al and TiC, will transform to Al and TiC when heated above 812°C. The theoretical weight fraction of TiC obtained by this reaction can be deduced from the intersection of the same two lines, and is found to be about 41 wt.%. Thus, given the density of TiC (4.93 g.cm^{-3} [3]) and Al (2.7 g.cm^{-3} [3]), the theoretical volume fraction of TiC in the composite is calculated to be 27.6 vol.%. It has to be noted that using Al as an additional precursor material leads to lower volume fractions of reinforcement.

3 TYPICAL MICROSTRUCTURE OF MMC OBTAINED AFTER IN-SITU SYNTHESIS

As illustrated in Figure 2, an homogeneous microstructure is observed for the Al-TiC composite obtained after 1 min of isothermal treatment at 1000°C. MCC domains consist in the Al-rich solid solution reinforced with a high volume fraction of TiC. Despite this high volume fraction no clustering of particles is evidenced by Transmission Electronic Microscopy (TEM): the particles of a few tenth of nanometers in size are individualized and surrounded by the Al solid solution. In order to perform a complete and detailed characterization, the composite is dissociated by an acidic etching procedure and both the liquid solution; the evolved gases and the residual solid particles are then analyzed separately. The procedure is detailed elsewhere [4].

Figure 2: Representative view of the Al-TiC composite microstructure (1000x) obtained after 1min isothermal treatment at 1000°C of an Al₃Ti-C mixture.

This dissociated analysis of the composite allows a more detailed characterization of the TiC reinforcing particles. As an example, the particle size distribution can be obtained after image analysis on micrograph obtained by Scanning Electronic Microscopy. In the present case, after 1 min of heat treatment at 1000°C, a very narrow distribution is obtained (from 15 to 50 nm) with an average size of TiC particles that is found to be about 30 nm (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Size distribution of TiC particles reinforcement from SEM observations obtained after 1min isothermal treatment at 1000°C of an Al₃Ti-C mixture and dissolution of the Al matrix by selective acidic etching.

The peculiar microstructure obtained after in-situ synthesis of both the Al matrix and TiC reinforcing particles leads to remarkable mechanical properties. Some results have already been reported for a dilute Al-TiC composite characterized by a 22 vol.% of reinforcement, a Young's modulus of 106 GPa, $\sigma_{e0.2\%}$ of 450 MPa, Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) of 490 MPa and a maximum elongation of 6% [4]. This original compromise between strength and ductility, despite the high volume fraction of particles, is attributed to the absence of particle clustering and the quality of the interface between matrix and reinforcement that is created in-situ.

4 GENERALIZATION TO OTHER SYSTEMS

The results obtained in the case of synthesis of Al-TiC composite from high temperature reaction between Al₃Ti and C highlight the potential of this original process in order to produce composite with interesting and original properties. A deep and clear understanding of the mechanisms allowing the production of the Al-TiC composite microstructure is necessary in order to generalize and to adapt the process with success to other systems

There are currently 2 patents pending as a result of the development of this new process route leading to new MMC materials.

5 CONCLUSIONS

As a conclusion, we have demonstrated in the present paper the feasibility of a new route for reactive synthesis of PRMMC materials. The process consists in a chemical reaction between two precursors leading to the in-situ production of both the matrix and the particles of reinforcement. To determine if a matrix/reinforcement couple is suitable for this new synthesis route, several criteria have to be considered. Among them one can cite: the topology of the phase equilibria and the mechanism of reaction.

The main advantages of this in-situ reactive synthesis are the followings. Because the reinforcement particles are formed in-situ by a nucleation/growth mechanism, the homogeneity of the microstructure is easily obtained (no clustering of particles) and the interface with the matrix is free of oxide layers. The number of defects in the ceramic particles is reduced, as they do not undergo high-energy milling. Finally the simplicity of the manufacturing route has to be highlighted. As an example,

nano-sized reinforcement could be obtained in the composite material without any handling of nano-sized powders as precursors.

Finally, the mechanical results obtained in the case of an Al-matrix composite reinforced by nano-sized TiC particles have shown an original and interesting compromise between high strength properties and a ductile behavior with 6% elongation, even with 22 vol.% of reinforcement.

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